

SUSCEPTIBILITY OF MICROBIAL ISOLATES FROM PHONE SCREENS TO ANTIBIOTICS AND DISINFECTANT AGENTS

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ABSTRACT

Smart phones with touch screens are now common place with students today. The microbial density of mobile phone screens of undergraduate students were examined using standard bacteriological methods. The susceptibility of the bacterial isolates was carried out using disc diffusion method. The efficacy of alcohols as a potential phone screen disinfectant was tested on the isolates. Six species of bacteria as well as five (5) species of fungi were isolated. The bacteria genera were *Klebsiella* spp (60%), *Micrococcus* spp (60%), *Bacillus* spp (65%), *Staphylococcus* spp (85%), *Proteus* spp (65%) and *Escherichia coli* (60%). The isolated fungi include *Aspergillus niger*, *Penicillium* spp, *Mucor* spp, *Candida* spp and *Cladosporium* spp. The organisms were generally susceptible to commercially available antibiotics. Among the antibiotics ciprofloxacin (5µg) exhibited the highest zone of inhibition (22mm) on *Staphylococcus aureus*. (14mm). Isopropyl alcohol and ethyl ethanol at a concentration of 70 % showed 100% elimination of microbial contaminants of phone screens. This study showed that all mobile phones under consideration were infected by several microbes. Hand hygiene and regular phone sanitization with alcohol based products is therefore recommended.

Keywords: Phone screens, Microorganisms, Antibiotics, Students

INTRODUCTION

With the advancement in technology, the use of mobile devices have grown sporadically (Viveka, 2017). Until the late 1980s, most mobile phones were quite large that they were permanently installed in vehicles as car phones or in standing phone boots along the streets. These devices, once cumbersome have become so miniaturized that they fit in palms and pockets, and are easily accessible to the owner (Ya'aba *et al.*, 2020). In addition to the standard voice function of a telephone, a mobile phone supports many other services such as Short Message Service (SMS), email, internet access and Multimedia Messaging Service (MMS) for the exchange of photos and videos between billions of users around the world (Anibijuwon *et al.*, 2015).

Nowadays, manufacturers have included other functions such as: camera for digital imaging, GPS for map and location and fingerprint sensor making mobile phones an on-the-go necessity for people from all walks of life including students who make use of the variety of applications (apps) and software to ease their learning process. Needless to say, mobile phones have emerged as a must-have technology for everyone in the twenty-first (21st) century (Adhikari *et al.*, 2018). At present, Africa has the largest growth rate of cellular subscribers in the world and projections by the telecommunication industry shows that these figures are on the increase. Nigeria occupies a chunk of the African telecommunication market as the availability of prepaid or pay-as-you-go services where the subscribers do not have to commit to a long-term contract has helped fuel the growth on a monumental scale (Ibrahim *et al.*, 2014).

It is estimated that a large population of undergraduate students use one form of mobile device or more as a key social tool which they rely on as an address book to keep in contact with family and friends, clocks, organizers, reminders and calculator (Anibijuwon *et al.*, 2015). This is against the background that many undergraduates have little to no regard for personal hygiene and may overlook the potential health hazard which these devices pose. The continual handling of these mobile phones without proper cleaning makes it an ideal niche for microbes especially those associated with the skin, thus resulting in a spread of autochthonous and allochthonous microbiota from user to user. Owing to the advantages of mobile phones, their safety in relation to health is often undermined. The incessant handling of these devices by owners – as well as family, friends, acquaintances, strangers makes it a mobile petri dish for diverse numbers of microorganisms (Karabay *et al.*, 2007; Anupam *et al.*, 2020).

Among other sources, dust is an important route of airborne transmission. It is not uncommon for pathogens to adhere to dust particles and contribute to the number of airborne pathogens when dust is dispersed by some disturbances. The suspended dust particles would later settle, along with the pathogens they carry, on surfaces especially inanimate materials such as mobile phones. This could be a potential source of epidemic outbreak of infectious diseases (Prescott *et al.*, 2008; Ya'aba *et al.*, 2020). One can therefore safely conclude that mobile phones are potential reservoirs of pathogenic

microorganisms and can serve as an extraneous source of infection among users. Mobile phones may act as fomites for the indirect contact transmission of a high infective load of pathogenic microorganisms such as *Staphylococcus* spp and *Escherichia coli* (Adetona *et al.*, 2009; Ovca *et al.*, 2012).

Compared to the other stationary objects, mobile phones have become part of so-called emotional technology and are frequently used in the environment with heavy microbial presence. Constant handling of phones by different users, heat generated by the phones and humid conditions creates a prime breeding ground for many microorganisms. The ability of the microbes to survive on the contact surfaces of mobile phones makes it one of the important fomites that may play a role in the spread of different microorganisms from user to user. Furthermore, hand washing may not be performed often during the course of a working day and therefore the likelihood of the mobile phones as a potential source of microbial contamination and transmission is indisputable. Bacterial cells could readily adhere to mobile phone surfaces and could form organized colonies (Beveridge *et al.* 1997; Viveka, 2017). Hands play a major role in the transmission of infection in healthcare institutions in industrial settings such as food industries and also in all communities and domestic settings (Aiello and Larson, 2002). Hands and instrument used by workers serve as vectors for the transmission of micro-organisms (Brady *et al.*, 2007; Viveka, 2017). The increasing use of mobile phone in our environment is one of the reasons why many scientists believe some disease rates are on the rise (Singh *et al.*, 2010; Suganya and Sumath, 2012)

Safety is a legitimate concern to the users of wireless equipment, particularly with regards to possible hazards caused by microbial contamination. Smart mobile phones are extensively used by the students of the Department of Microbiology, Faculty of Life Sciences, University of Benin, Benin City, for variety of purposes. Despite the extensive use, there is inadequate information on the bacterial contamination of the mobile phones owned by these students.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sample Collection: The samples were collected from the mobile phones of students of the Department of Microbiology, University of Benin, Benin City. A total of two hundred (200) randomly selected devices were swabbed for the study from the following study groups; one hundred (100) each from both female and male students. Informed consents were obtained from all participants whose phones were used for the study. Sterile cotton swab sticks moistened with sterile normal saline were used to collect the specimen from the screen of each device in an S-shaped manner. All samples were transported from collection area within ten minutes to the laboratory for analysis. The samples were bulked with ten samples making one unit and labelled BI-B10 for boys and G1-G10 for girls.

Isolation of Microorganisms: Each S-shaped swab sample was placed in 3ml of peptone water and thoroughly shaken to ensure uniformity of mixture. One (1) ml of the suspension was aseptically pipetted and transferred onto prepared nutrient agar and potato dextrose agar in petri dishes. The agar were incubated at room temperature for 48h and 72h (for bacteria and fungi respectively). Microbial colonies were subsequently counted and expressed as colony-forming unit per milliliter (CFU/ml) of the sample analyzed. Bacterial isolates from nutrient agar and fungal isolates from potato dextrose agar were sub-cultured to obtain pure isolates. Bacterial isolates with distinct colony characteristics were sub-cultured aseptically using wire loop and streaking on the surface of freshly prepared nutrient agar plates and incubated at room temperature for 48 h. Purified isolates were then characterized and identified based on their colonial characteristics, cell morphology and biochemical tests (Cheesebrough, 2000; Holt *et al.*, 2000). Potato dextrose agar (PDA) media amended with streptomycin to inhibit the growth of bacteria was employed for the isolation of fungi by spread plate method using direct plating techniques. All the plates were incubated at room temperature for 5 days. Fungal isolates were identified using cultural and microscopic features. Slides were prepared from pure cultures and viewed under the microscope at X40 magnification after adding lactophenol blue. The fungal colonies were identified as described by Barnett and Hunter (1998).

Antibacterial Susceptibility Test: The standardization of the inoculum was done according to the method of Cheesebrough (2000). First a turbidity standard equivalent to McFarland 0.5 was prepared. This was done by mixing 0.6ml of 1% barium chloride solution to 99.4ml of 1% v/v sulphuric acid solution. The inocula to be used was compared with this standard in bright light. The antibiotic susceptibility testing was carried out using disc-diffusion technique (Kirby-Bauer, 1996). The antibiotics used in this study were obtained from Oxoid, Basingstoke, UK. They include; augmentin (10 μ g), gentamycin (10 μ g), amoxicillin (10 μ g), septrin (5 μ g), chloramphenicol (15 μ g), ciprofloxacin (5 μ g) and streptomycin (15 μ g). With a sterile wire loop 3-5 well isolated colonies of the test organism was touched and emulsified in sterile saline. A sterile swab was then used to inoculate a plate of Mueller Hinton agar. The appropriate antibiotic disc were then placed on the agar surface, with sterile forceps and gently pressed for contact with the agar. The plates were inverted and thereafter incubated overnight. After the incubation period, the diameter of zone of inhibition (clearance) was measured using a metre rule. The zones were recorded to the nearest millimetre.

Effect of Disinfectants on Microbial Proliferation on Phone Screens: A total of twelve phones randomly obtained from the students was employed. Agents for disinfection were distilled water, dry paper towel, ethyl alcohol (70%) and isopropyl alcohol (70%). The microbial load of the phone screens were taken before and after the application of the agent and the pathogen elimination efficiency determined.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 shows the microbial population of the phone screen samples examined. The total heterotrophic bacterial and fungal count ranged from 3.8x10² to 8.3x10² CFU/ml and 2.2x10² to 5.6x10² CFU/ml respectively for male users (BI-B10). Conversely, samples obtained from female users – labelled G1 to G10 – were found to contain a total heterotrophic bacterial count ranging from 1.6x10² to 5.3x10² CFU/ml. The corresponding fungal count for this group ranged from 1.1 x 10² to 3.6 x 10².

In Table 2 is shown the distribution of bacterial isolates with *Staphylococcus* spp having the highest (85%) occurrence. *Escherichia coli* and *Bacillus* spp were more prevalent in female phone screens compared to the males. Table 3 shows the distribution of the fungal isolates in the samples swabbed from all phone screens. The fungal isolates were *Aspergillus niger*, *Candida* spp, *Penicillium* spp, *Cladosporium* spp and *Mucor* spp. *Candida* spp was the least prevalent among these fungi from phone screens.

Table 4 shows the susceptibility of the bacterial isolates to commercially available antibiotics.

Among the antibiotics ciprofloxacin (5µg) exhibited the highest zone of inhibition (22mm) on *Staphylococcus aureus*. The least zone of inhibition (11mm) was shown by streptomycin (15µg) and chloramphenicol (15µg) on *Micrococcus* spp and *Klebsiella* spp respectively. *Escherichia coli* was fully susceptible (20mm) to Gentamycin (10µg) and Amoxicillin (10µg) with a clearance zone of 19mm. In Table 5 is shown the elimination efficiency of cleaning agents on mobile phone screens. The cleaning efficacy of sterile distilled water was in the range 18 to 29 % while dry paper towel was 9 to 31 %. In comparison ethyl – and isopropyl alcohol had 100 % elimination efficiency of microbial isolates from phone screens.

Studies on bacterial contamination of mobile phones and their antibiotic susceptibility pattern among students by Tagoe *et al.* (2011) revealed that all sampled mobile phones had high contamination of varieties of bacteria with high resistance to common antibiotics. This is corroborated in this study with low zones of inhibition suggesting possible antimicrobial resistance.

Mobile phones are a veritable reservoir for microorganisms that may result in infection due to the personal nature and proximity to users' body parts such as faces, ears, lips and hands. These organisms may probably have found their way on the phone from the skin and from hand to hand. This is because some of the isolated bacteria such as *Staphylococcus aureus* in this study are the normal microbiota of the skin as advanced by earlier researchers (Amira and Abdallahi, 2010).

Frequent handling by many users with different hygiene profiles and regular skin contact with the phone surfaces may have resulted in the frequency and the degree of population of the isolates in this

study. This has many health implications as the microorganisms isolated are known to cause illnesses ranging from pimples and boils to pneumonia as well as opportunistic infections. The isolation of *Staphylococcus* spp (85%), *Bacillus* spp (65%), *Klebsiella* spp (60%), *Proteus* spp (65%), *Micrococcus* spp (60%) and *Escherichia coli* (60%) corroborates the findings of Ibrahim *et al.* (2014) who noted that the main bacteria isolates frequently associated with mobile phones are from the normal skin microbiota with a few exceptions. The considerable isolation of *Bacillus* spp in this study might be related to its ability to form spores which can resist environmental changes and certain chemical disinfectants.

Staphylococcus spp had the highest isolation rate of 85% which may be attributed to its ubiquitous nature. Hand activities including touching of contaminated objects, toilet environs, shaking of hands could be major contributing factors to the presence of this potential pathogen. Mobile phones contaminated with bacteria such as *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* may cause hospital infections, and may serve as a vehicle for the spread of nosocomial infections. Users of mobile phones are not restricted to a particular geographical location as individuals move around to public places such as markets, homes, hospitals, banks, and schools. They could therefore be a potential cause of the spread of the infection in the community as propounded in a similar study by Karabay *et al.*, (2007).

The isolated bacterial species can be transferred from person to person or from inanimate object such as computers, door knobs, desktops and ballpoint pens to hands and vice versa (Gragil *et al.*, 2006). The use of mobile phones by lecturers in the classroom, technologists in the laboratories and students may have serious hygiene consequences, because unlike fixed phones, mobile phones are often carried about within and outside the classrooms and laboratories (Gragil *et al.*, 2006).

The occurrence of fungal species may not be surprising since they are spore producing. Thus their spores readily attached to the phone screens. Some of these micro-fungi like *Aspergillus* and *Penicillium* are known to cause respiratory diseases, irritations, allergy and possibly result in asthmatic attack. The habit of holding a mobile phone with unclean hands renders the surface greasy

and sticky thus possibly allowing the growth and multiplication of varied micro-fungal colonies. The variations and number however is also contingent on humidity, temperature and other environmental factors favoring their growth and attachment to the screens (Singh *et al.*, 2010).

Most bacteria such as *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Acinetobacter*, *Escherichia coli* and *Shigella* can survive on dry surfaces for months. Against this backdrop phone manufacturers only give general maintenance instructions without specific recommendations on cleaning and disinfection. Considering the shape of mobile phones and their screens which can harbor microorganisms as established in this study, it is imperative to disinfect them regularly to avoid trans-infection. Although water and dry paper towel can remove or dislodge some organisms through abrasion, they were generally inefficient at sanitization. The result obtained with 70 % ethyl and isopropyl alcohols is in consonance with Ovca *et al.* (2012). Both achieved 100% elimination efficiency after 10 min. Alcohols deactivate microbial cells by protein inactivation. Therefore, given that some students have poor hand hygiene especially in snacking and after toilet usage it is now imperative to sanitize phones regularly to avoid contamination with faecal bacteria which in many cases can cause gastroenteritis and food poisoning.

CONCLUSION

The study showed that the bacterial and fungal isolates from the mobile phones were mostly skin flora as well as potentially epidemiologically important pathogens. Some factors like regular cleaning, presence of scratches, age of the phone and sharing mobile phones with others may alter the occurrence of different species of bacteria on the touch pad. It is evident from this study that the undergraduate students are using modern technology for multiple purposes and they may be unaware of the adverse health effects associated with unhygienic use of this technology. Strict adherence to infection control, such as regular hand washing and regular cleaning of phone screens with disinfectant is advocated.

Table 1: Microbial population of phone screen samples

Sample ID	TBC (x10 ² cfu/ml)	FC (x10 ² cfu/ml)
B1	5.6	3.8
B2	4.4	3.0
B3	6.2	4.2
B4	8.3	5.6
B5	3.3	2.2
B6	5.7	3.9
B7	7.1	4.8
B8	4.5	3.1
B9	3.8	2.6
B10	6.1	4.1
G1	3.6	2.4
G2	4.1	2.8
G3	2.6	1.8
G4	1.8	1.2
G5	2.3	1.6
G6	1.8	1.2
G7	5.3	3.6
G8	3.9	2.7
G9	4.2	2.9
G10	1.6	1.1

Key: TBC = Total bacterial count, B1-B10 = Bulked samples from boys, FC = Fungal count, G1-G10 = Bulked samples from girls.

Table 2: Distribution of bacteria isolates on phone screens

Sample ID	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>Proteus</i> spp.	<i>Klebsiella</i> spp.	<i>Bacillus</i> spp.	<i>Staphylococcus</i> spp.	<i>Micrococcus</i> spp.
B1	+	-	+	-	+	-
B2	+	+	-	+	+	-
B3	-	+	-	+	+	-
B4	+	+	+	-	-	+
B5	+	-	+	+	+	-
B6	-	+	+	-	+	+
B7	-	+	-	+	+	+
B8	-	+	+	-	-	+
B9	+	+	+	-	+	+
B10	+	-	-	+	+	-
G1	-	+	-	+	+	+
G2	+	-	-	+	+	+
G3	+	+	-	+	+	+
G4	-	+	+	-	+	+
G5	-	+	+	+	+	-
G6	+	-	+	+	-	+
G7	+	+	-	+	+	-
G8	-	+	+	-	+	+
G9	+	-	+	+	+	+
G10	+	-	+	+	+	-
%	60	65	60	65	85	60

KEY: B= boys, G= girls. + = positive. - = negative.

Table 3: Distribution of fungal isolates on phone screens

Sample ID	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	<i>Candida</i> spp.	<i>Penicillium</i> spp.	<i>Cladosporium</i> spp.	<i>Mucor</i> spp.
B1	+	-	+	+	-
B2	+	-	+	-	+
B3	-	+	-	+	+
B4	+	-	+	+	-
B5	-	-	+	-	+
B6	+	-	+	+	-
B7	+	+	-	+	+
B8	+	-	-	+	+
B9	+	-	+	-	+
B10	+	-	-	-	+
G1	-	+	+	+	+
G2	-	-	+	+	-
G3	+	+	-	-	+

G4	+	+	+	+	-
G5	-	-	+	+	+
G6	+	+	-	-	+
G7	-	-	+	+	-
G8	+	+	+	+	-
G9	-	+	+	+	+
G10	-	+	-	+	+
% occurrence	60	45	65	70	70

KEY: B= boys, G= girls. + = positive. - = negative.

Table 4: Susceptibility of bacterial isolates to antibiotics.

Isolates	Augmentin (10µg)	Gentamycin (10µg)	Streptomycin (15 µg)	Septtrin (5 µg)	Chloramphenicol (15 µg)	Ciprofloxacin (5 µg)	Amoxicillin (10 µg)
<i>E. coli</i>	16	20	16	18	12	20	19
<i>Proteus</i> spp.	19	17	19	16	18	17	17
<i>Klebsiella</i> spp.	15	13	15	14	11	16	14
<i>Bacillus</i> spp.	13	17	12	18	14	19	15
<i>Staphylococcus</i> spp.	21	17	18	19	16	22	17
<i>Micrococcus</i> spp.	14	16	11	14	18	18	14

Table 5: Effect of cleaning agents on pathogen removal from phone screens

Sample	Cleaning agent	Total CFU Before cleaning (x10 ²)	Total CFU After cleaning (x10 ²)	Elimination Efficiency (%)
1		5.0	4.1	18.0
2	Water	7.5	5.3	29.0
3		8.0	6.2	22.5
4		2.2	2.0	9.0
5	Dry paper towel	2.6	1.8	31.0
6		2.1	1.9	10
7		3.2	0.0	0.0
8	Ethyl alcohol	2.0	0.0	0.0
9		2.5	0.0	0.0
10		1.5	0.0	0.0
11	Isopropyl alcohol	2.8	0.0	0.0
12		3.4	0.0	0.0

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